

Synthesis of some new chalcones, pyrazolines and acetyl pyrazolines derived from piperonal and halogenohydroxy acetophenones as antimicrobial agents

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Abstract : New chalcones, pyrazolines and acetyl pyrazolines were synthesized and characterized by IR, ^1H NMR, Mass spectral and halogen, nitrogen analysis. The compounds were screened for antibacterial (*Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) and antifungal (*Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum* and *Fusarium moneliforme*) activity. Some of the compounds showed better activity than standard compound used for comparison.

Keywords : Chalcones, pyrazolines, acetylpyrazolines, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity.

Introduction

Biologically active chalcones, pyrazolines and acetyl pyrazolines have played an important role in medicinal chemistry. The presence of α,β -unsaturated keto function in chalcones is found to be responsible for their antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Chalcones are wide spread component in all parts of plants and are important as flower pigment, growth regulators, phytoalexins and animal toxins¹. Number of chalcones having hydroxy, methoxy, isopentyl group in different position have been isolated from various plant materials and some of them possess wide range of biological activity such as germicidal², bactericidal³, fungicidal⁴, carcinogenic⁵, antibacterial⁶, antifungal⁷, anticancer⁸, antitumour⁹, antitubercular¹⁰, antiviral¹¹, antiulcer¹², antipeptic ulcer¹³, aldose reductase inhibitors i.e. antidiabetic agents¹⁴. In recent year chalcones possessing inhibitory effect on Rat Lens Aldose Reductase [RLAR] and Rat Platelet Aggregation¹⁵ were studied.

2-Pyrazolines derivatives have been found to possess wide range of therapeutic activity such as antibacterial¹⁶, antifungal¹⁷, anti-HIV¹⁸, antimicrobial¹⁹, anticonvulsant²⁰, analgesic²¹, antianalgesic²², anticancer²³, antidepressant²⁴, antiviral²⁵, antioxidant²⁶, anti-inflammatory²⁷ and cardiovascular²⁸ activity. Since wide range of bioactivity found in chalcones in the present work we have prepared

some new chalcones, pyrazolines and acetyl pyrazolines having halogenohydroxyphenyl and methylenedioxyphenyl moiety.

New 2'-hydroxychalcones were synthesized starting from halohydroxy substituted acetophenone and piperonal. 2'-Hydroxychalcones were then subjected to react with hydrazine hydrate in ethyl alcohol yielded pyrazolines while *N*-acetylpyrazolines were formed when acetic acid was used as a solvent instead of ethyl alcohol. *N*-Acetyl pyrazolines were also prepared by refluxing 2-pyrazolines with acetic acid for 1 h. Newly synthesized chalcones, pyrazolines and acetyl pyrazolines were characterized by IR, ^1H NMR, Mass spectral and halogen, nitrogen analysis. The compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Biological activity :

Antibacterial (*Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) activity were evaluated by Agar cup method^{29,30} and antifungal (*Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum* and *Fusarium moneliforme*) activity was evaluated by Poison plate method³¹. Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm for antibacterial activity data and Poison plate method data for antifungal activity is given in Table 1. Results shows that compounds **2h**, **2i**, **2j**, **3a**, **3h** and **4b** are having significant activity for *B. subtilis*.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds

Sl no	Antibacterial activity (Zone of inhibition in mm)			Antifungal activity			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	<i>F. moniliforme</i>
2a	8	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	RG	RG
2b	-ve	8	8	-ve	+ve	RG	RG
2c	-ve	-ve	-ve	RG	+ve	+ve	-ve
2d	-ve	20	-ve	-ve	RG	-ve	-ve
2e	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
2f	10	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve
2g	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	RG	-ve
2h	8	18	22	-ve	-ve	RG	RG
2i	-ve	-ve	34	-ve	RG	-ve	-ve
2j	-ve	20	38	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
3a	7	15	16	-ve	RG	-ve	-ve
3b	-ve	14	-ve	-ve	RG	RG	-ve
3c	-ve	12	8	-ve	+ve	RG	RG
3d	-ve	14	10	-ve	-ve	RG	-ve
3e	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve
3f	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	RG	RG	-ve
3g	-ve	-ve	7	-ve	+ve	+ve	RG
3h	9	16	14	-ve	+ve	RG	RG
3i	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	RG	RG	-ve
4a	-ve	-ve	9	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
4b	-ve	18	14	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
4c	-ve	14	7	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve
4d	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve
4e	-ve	-ve	10	-ve	RG	RG	RG
4f	-ve	10	-ve	RG	RG	RG	RG
4g	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
4h	12	11	10	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve
4i	-ve	10	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Penicillin	10	24	14				

where -ve No Antibacterial activity

-ve No growth, Antifungal activity observed RG Reduced growth (less active) +ve Fungal growth, No Antifungal activity

Compounds **2d**, **2h**, **2j**, **3h** and **4b** showed moderate activity for *S. aureus* and for *E. coli*, compounds **2f**, **2h**, **3h** and **4h** are having significant activity.

The compounds **2d**, **2e**, **2g**, **2h**, **2j**, **3a**, **3b**, **3g**, **3i** and **4d** showed antifungal activity. In general compounds having two chloro or one chloro and one iodo substituent in their structure are having significant antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillary tube

and were uncorrected. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Bruker IFS 66V spectrometer with KBr pellets ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Gemini-200 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and Mass spectra were recorded on VG 7070H mass spectrometer. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel plates and the spots were developed in iodine chamber.

General method of synthesis of chalcones (2a-j) :

A mixture of halohydroxyacetophenone (0.01 mol) and piperonal (0.01 mol) were dissolved in ethyl alcohol (15

Note

Compd.	R	R ₁	R ₂
a	I	H	Cl
b	I	H	Br
c	I	H	CH ₃
d	Br	H	Cl
e	Br	CH ₃	Cl
f	I	CH ₃	Cl
g	Br	H	CH ₃
h	Cl	OH	Cl
i	Br	OH	Br
j	I	OH	I

Scheme of chalcones, pyrazolines and acetyl pyrazolines derived from piperonal.

ml) under stirring and aqueous KOH (50%, 12 ml) was added drop wise. The reaction mixture was kept at 40 °C for 14–16 h, and then was diluted with water and acidified with HCl. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised by using acetic acid to get chalcones (2a-j) in dark yellow needle shaped crystals.

General method of synthesis of 2-pyrazolines (3a-i) :

A mixture of chalcone (2a-i) (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (98%, 0.02 mol) in ethyl alcohol (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The solid mass separated

was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethyl alcohol to get 2-pyrazolines (3a-i) in colourless crystals.

General method of synthesis of N-acetyl pyrazolines (4a-i) :

A mixture of chalcone (2a-i) (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (98%, 0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The solid mass separated was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid to get acetyl pyrazolines (4a-i).

Same *N*-acetyl pyrazolines were prepared from pyrazoline, on heating pyrazoline in acetic acid for 1 h yielded *N*-acetyl pyrazolines (4a-i) in pale yellow crystals.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2a) :

Yield 85%, m.p. 168 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3066 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1159 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.06 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 7.10–7.94 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.88 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.86 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 12.5 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{IClO}_4$: I and Cl, 37.88. Found : I and Cl, 38.42.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-bromophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2b) :

Yield 80%, m.p. 146 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3064 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1157 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.15 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 7.12–7.94 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.86 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.91 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 12.15 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{IBrO}_4$: I and Br, 43.72. Found : I and Br, 43.28.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2c) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 160 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2898 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1558 (C=C), 1151 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 2.34 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 6.05 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.21–7.90 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.85 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.89 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.67 (1H, s, Ar-OH); EI-MS (m/z) : 408 (M^+ , 70), 391 (4), 380 (2), 287 (6), 260 (12), 175 (12), 148 (100). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{IO}_4$: I, 31.09. Found : I, 31.54.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2d) :

Yield 87%, m.p. 180 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3072 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1569 (C=C), 1164 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.10 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.16–7.94 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.84 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.92 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.61 (1H, s, Ar-OH); EI-MS (m/z) : 382, (M^+ , 22), 286 (2), 261 (2), 250 (50), 235 (88), 206 (3), 194 (8), 179 (16), 166 (10), 148 (100). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrClO}_4$: Br and Cl, 30.23. Found : Br and Cl, 30.10.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-methyl-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2e) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 224 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2904 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1571 (C=C), 1186 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR

(CDCl_3) δ : 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.08 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.25–7.90 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.86 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.88 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.55 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrClO}_4$: Br and Cl, 29.16. Found : Br and Cl, 29.43.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-4'-methyl-5'-chlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2f) :

Yield 78%, m.p. 154 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3298 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1556 (C=C), 1199 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 2.35 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.12 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.10–7.92 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.84 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.90 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.60 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{IClO}_4$: I and Cl, 36.68. Found : I and Cl, 36.29.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2g) :

Yield 80%, m.p. 142 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3050 (OH), 1633 (C=O), 1560 (C=C), 1157 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 2.30 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 6.08 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.15–7.94 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.86 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.90 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.70 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrO}_4$: Br, 22.12. Found : Br, 21.75.

1-(2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichlorophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2h) :

Yield 80%, m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3462 (Ar-OH), 2993 (Ar-OH), 1633 (C=O), 1558 (C=C), 1220 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.06 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.15–7.91 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.86 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.95 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.17 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 14.04 (1H, s, Ar-OH); EI-MS (m/z) : 352 (M^+ , 46), 335 (3), 324 (3), 231 (6), 205 (15), 175 (8), 162 (5), 148 (100). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_5$: Cl, 20.08. Found : Cl, 20.52.

1-(2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dibromophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2i) :

Yield 78%, m.p. 200 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3683 (Ar-OH), 3402 (Ar-OH), 1631 (C=O), 1562 (C=C), 1203 (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.10 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.83–7.96 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.85 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 7.93 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.24 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 14.00 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{Br}_2\text{O}_5$: Br, 36.15. Found : Br, 36.50.

1-(2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-di-iodophenyl)-3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2j) :

Yield 75%, m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3675 (Ar-OH), 3405 (Ar-OH), 1633 (C=O), 1568 (C=C), 1202 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 6.06 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.25–7.92 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.84 (1H, d, H_α , J 16 Hz), 8.05 (1H, d, H_β , J 16 Hz), 13.20 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 14.05 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{I}_2\text{O}_5$: I, 47.35. Found : I, 46.90.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3a) :

Yield 86%, m.p. 174 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3325 (OH), 1602 (C=N), 1178 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.07 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.47 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.20 (1H, dd, CH), 5.95 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.70 (1H, s, N-H), 6.75–7.66 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.01 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClIN}_2\text{O}_3$: I and Cl, 36.68; N, 6.33. Found : I and Cl, 36.27; N, 6.18.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-bromophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3b) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 102 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3330 (OH), 1605 (C=N), 1180 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.06 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.47 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.35 (1H, dd, CH), 5.95 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.75 (1H, s, N-H), 6.75–7.66 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.10 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{IBrN}_2\text{O}_3$: I and Br, 42.45; N, 5.75. Found : I and Br, 42.95; N, 5.82.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-methylphenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3c) :

Yield 78%, m.p. 124 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3334 (Ar-OH), 1606 (C=N), 1220 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 2.15 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.15 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.60 (1H, dd, H_B), 4.95 (1H, dd, CH), 5.95 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.80 (1H, s, N-H), 6.85–7.65 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.50 (1H, s, Ar-OH); GC-MS (m/z) : 422 (M^+ , 100), 405 (26), 301 (18), 174 (17), 148 (37), 118 (18), 104 (15), 89 (20), 77 (21), 65 (21), 51 (18). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{IN}_2\text{O}_3$: I, 30.06; N, 6.63. Found : I, 30.42; N, 6.30.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3d) :

Yield 80%, m.p. 142 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3328 (OH), 1608 (C=N), 1178 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.06 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.50 (1H, dd, H_B), 4.90 (1H, dd, CH),

5.90 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.80 (1H, s, N-H), 6.80–7.71 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.02 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrClN}_2\text{O}_3$: Br and Cl, 29.16; N, 7.08. Found : Br and Cl, 28.78; N, 7.24.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-methyl-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3e) :

Yield 76%, m.p. 144 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3330 (Ar-OH), 1610 (C=N), 1188 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 2.15 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.20 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.61 (1H, dd, H_B), 4.92 (1H, dd, CH), 5.90 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.81 (1H, s, N-H), 6.86–7.71 (4H, m, Ar-H), 11.90 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrClN}_2\text{O}_3$: Br and Cl, 28.15; N, 6.84. Found : Br and Cl, 27.81; N, 6.50.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-4'-methyl-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3f) :

Yield 75%, m.p. 146 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3325 (Ar-OH), 1610 (C=N), 1202 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 2.16 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.21 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.60 (1H, dd, H_B), 4.90 (1H, dd, CH), 15.92 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.82 (1H, s, N-H), 6.83–7.70 (4H, m, Ar-H), 11.05 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{IClN}_2\text{O}_3$: I and Cl, 35.55; N, 6.13. Found : I and Cl, 35.83; N, 6.22.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3g) :

Yield 80%, m.p. 98 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3331 (Ar-OH), 1605 (C=N), 1225 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 2.17 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.12 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.62 (1H, dd, H_B), 4.92 (1H, dd, CH), 5.91 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.82 (1H, s, N-H), 6.82–7.65 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.86 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3$: Br, 21.30; N, 7.47. Found : Br, 21.02; N, 7.32.

3-(2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3h) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 130 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3550–3319 (Ar-OH), 1618 (C=N), 1209 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 3.40 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.95 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.20 (1H, dd, CH), 5.95 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.70 (1H, s, N-H), 6.85–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H), 11.75 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 13.60 (1H, s, Ar-OH); EI-MS (m/z) : 367 (M^+ , 100). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: Cl, 19.31; N, 7.63. Found : Cl, 19.82; N, 7.84.

3-(2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dibromophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-pyrazoline (3i) :

Yield 76%, m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3552-3320 (Ar-OH), 1618 (C=N), 1211 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{CDCl}_3)$ δ : 3.41 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.92 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.18 (1H, dd, CH), 5.92 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.70 (1H, s, N-H), 6.85-7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H), 10.95 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 11.85 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: Br, 35.04; N, 6.14. Found : Br, 34.75; N, 6.02.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-acetyl pyrazoline (4a) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 238 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3534, 3319 (-OH), 1675 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1618 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1210 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{CDCl}_3)$ δ : 2.46 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.22 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.90 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.15 (1H, dd, CH), 5.95 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.70-7.20 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.30 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClIN}_2\text{O}_4$: I and Cl, 33.53; N, 5.77. Found : I and Cl, 33.49; N, 5.78.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-bromophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-acetyl pyrazoline (4b) :

Yield 80%, m.p. 232 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3319 (-OH), 1675 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1620 (C=N), 1368 (C-N), 1202 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{CDCl}_3)$ δ : 2.36 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.22 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.90 (1H, dd, H_B), 4.90 (1H, dd, CH), 5.95 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.70-7.20 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.55 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{IBrN}_2\text{O}_4$: I and Br, 39.08; N, 5.29. Found : I and Br, 39.50; N, 5.21.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-5'-methylphenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-N-acetyl pyrazoline (4c) :

Yield 84%, m.p. 220 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3134 (Ar-OH), 1670 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1614 (C=N), 1363 (C-N), 1166 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{DMSO})$ δ : 2.30 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.50 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.30 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.95 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.45 (1H, dd, CH), 6.00 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.80-7.75 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.20 (1H, s, Ar-OH); EI-MS (m/z) : 464 (M^+ , 100), 447 (4), 421 (58), 405 (26), 392 (2), 301(24), 295 (8), 275 (12), 260 (4), 235 (3), 221 (4), 205 (15), 190 (12), 177 (26), 162 (42). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{IN}_2\text{O}_4$: I, 27.22; N, 6.01. Found : I, 27.28; N, 6.27.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2-acetyl pyrazoline (4d) :

Yield 77%, m.p. 242 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3318 (Ar-OH), 1671 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1621 (C=N), 1371 (C-N), 1204

(C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{CDCl}_3)$ δ : 2.38 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.18 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.91 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.22 (1H, dd, CH), 5.90 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.71-7.18 (5H, m, Ar-H), 12.15 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrClN}_2\text{O}_4$: Br and Cl, 26.36; N, 6.40. Found : Br and Cl, 26.15; N, 6.74.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-methyl-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-N-acetyl pyrazoline (4e) :

Yield 72%, m.p. 194 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3294 (Ar-OH), 1667 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1612 (C=N), 1365 (C-N), 1191 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{DMSO})$ δ : 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.55 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.31 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.92 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.50 (1H, dd, CH), 6.04 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.82-7.75 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.18 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{BrClN}_2\text{O}_4$: Br and Cl, 25.54; N, 6.20. Found : Br and Cl, 25.82; N, 6.07.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-iodo-4'-methyl-5'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-N-acetyl pyrazoline (4f) :

Yield 75%, m.p. 216 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3280 (Ar-OH), 1667 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1618 (C=N), 1377 (C-N), 1198 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{DMSO})$ δ : 2.34 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.50 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.30 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.90 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.55 (1H, dd, CH), 6.09 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.82-7.77 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.05 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClIN}_2\text{O}_4$: I and Cl, 32.56; N, 5.62. Found : I and Cl, 32.16; N, 5.35.

3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedi-oxyphenyl)-N-acetyl pyrazoline (4g) :

Yield 76%, m.p. 210 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3130 (Ar-OH), 1671 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1610 (C=N), 1368 (C-N), 1195 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{DMSO})$ δ : 2.33 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.51 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.32 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.96 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.48 (1H, dd, CH), 6.08 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.80-7.77 (5H, m, Ar-H), 11.10 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_4$: Br, 19.15; N, 6.71. Found : Br, 19.62; N, 85.

3-(2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichlorophenyl)-5-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-N-acetyl pyrazoline (4h) :

Yield 76%, m.p. 276 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3022 (OH), 1643 (C=N), 1147 (C-O-C), 1299 (C-N); $^1\text{H NMR}(\text{DMSO})$ δ : 2.41 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.30 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.90 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.45 (1H, dd, CH), 6.00 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.80-7.55 (4H, m, Ar-H), 10.93 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 11.75 (1H, s, Ar-OH); EI-MS (m/z) : 408 (M^+ , 20), 366 (18), 326 (4), 298 (58), 270 (42), 266 (92), 255 (95), 245

(10), 241 (80), 237 (16), 225 (12), 211 (8), 205 (12), 199 (32), 189 (10), 184 (28), 177 (62), 169 (4), 162 (100). Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{14}Cl_2N_2O_5$: Cl, 17.35; N, 6.84. Found: Cl, 17.02; N, 6.53.

3-(2', 4'-Dihydroxy-3', 5'-bromophenyl)-5-(3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-N-acetyl pyrazoline (4i):

Yield 80%, m.p. 248 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2998 (OH), 1640 (C=N), 1167 (C-O-C), 1199 (CN); 1H NMR (DMSO) δ : 2.35 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 3.32 (1H, dd, H_A), 3.92 (1H, dd, H_B), 5.50 (1H, dd, CH), 6.06 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.82–7.58 (4H, m, Ar-H), 11.00 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 12.25 (1H, s, Ar-OH). Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{14}Br_2N_2O_5$: Br, 32.08; N, 5.62. Found: Br, 32.58; N, 5.46.

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References

- I. E. E. Conn, "The Biochemistry of Plants", Academic Press, New York, 1981, 7, 425; S. Ghosal and R. K. Chaudhari, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, 64, 888.
- J. Russel and H. Clarke, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3651.
- J. K. Eaton and R. G. Devies, *Am. Appl. Bio.*, 1950, 37, 473.
- N. P. Buu-Hoi and N. D. Xuong, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 39.
- S. C. Kushwaha, Dinkar and J. B. Lal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 82.
- M. B. Hogale, N. P. Dhole, A. R. Shelar and P. K. Pawar *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1986, 2, 55 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, 106, 32503a); J. Methew, A. Subba Rao and S. S. Rambhav, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, 53, 576; C. M. Devia, N. B. Pappano and N. B. Debattista, *Rev. Microbiol.*, 1998, 29, 307.
- H. Tsuchiya, M. Sato, M. Alkagiri, N. Takagi, Tanake and M. Linuma, *Pharmazie*, 1994, 49, 756.
- J. R. Dimmock, D. W. Elian, M. A. Beazely and N. M. Kandepu, *Current Med. Chem.*, 1999, 6, 1125; T. Yamakawa, H. Kagechika, E. Kawachi, Y. Hashimoto and K. Shudo, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1990, 33, 1430; V. K. Ahluwalia, L. Nayal, N. Kaila, S. Balu and A. K. Tahim, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, 26, 384.
- V. K. Ahluwalia, L. Nayak, N. Kalia, N. Bala and A. K. Tehim, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, 26, 384.
- R. Doshi, P. Kagthara and H. Parekh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, 38, 348; S. S. Bhatt, R. P. Bhamaria, (Mrs.) M. R. Patel, R. A. Bellare and C. V. Deliwala, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 694 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 78, 119650n).
- H. Ishitsuka, Y. Ninomiya, C. Ohsawa, M. Fujiu and Y. Suhara, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1982, 22, 617; Y. Ninomiya, N. Shimma and H. Ishitsuk, *Antiviral. Res.*, 1990, 13, 61.
- K. Kyogoku, K. Hatayama, S. Yokomori, R. Saiziki, S. Nakane, M. Sasajima, J. Jawadia, M. Ohzeki and I. Tanaka, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1979, 27, 2943.
- G. Rene D. Magnolato and Ron, *Phytochemistry*, 1986, 26, 1431.
- Severi Fabio, Benvenuti Stifania, Costantiho Luca, Vampa Gabriella, Melegari Michele and Antolini Luciano, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, 33, 859.
- Soon Sung Lim, Sang Hoon Jung, Jun Jt, Kuk Hyun Shin and Sam Rok Keum, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2000, 48, 1786.
- M. M. El-Kerdawy and A. A. El-Emam, *J. Chem. Soc. Pak.*, 1987, 9, 285 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, 107, 198165b); A. A. Regaila Hassan, N. Latif and I. H. Ibrahim, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1989, 30, 179 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, 112, 216775k).
- M. Shah, P. Patel, S. Korgaokar and H. Parekh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1996, 35, 1282.
- V. S. Jolly and M. Pathak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 68, 304; Akhlaq Waheed and Suroor Ahmad Khan, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, 11, 59.
- G. Gautham Shenoy, A. R. Bhat, G. Varadaraj Bhat and Mohan Kotian, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, 10, 197.
- S. S. Parmar, B. R. Pandey and C. Diwedi, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1974, 63, 1152 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 82, 259660u).
- Z. Brozozowsk and E. Pomarnacka, *Acta Pol. Pharm.*, 1980, 37, 1378.
- F. Manna, F. Chimenti, A. Balasco, M. L. Cenicola, M. D. Amioco, C. Parrilla, F. Rossi and E. Marmo, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, 27, 633; W. D. Solomon, Sam, T. K. Ravi and K. Annadurai, *Indian Drugs*, 1999, 36, 466.
- V. S. Jolly, G. D. Arora and Talwar Preeti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 1001.
- K. C. Joshi, Anshu Dandia and Sangeeta Khanna, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, 29, 933.
- D. V. Mane, V. P. Chavan, A. Mane, S. B. Bhawsar and M. S. Shingare, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2000, 9, 271.

26. M. Morigaki and N. Seto, Japan (kokal), 1988, 63115866.
27. R. H. Udipi, S. N. Rao and A. R. Bhat, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1998, 7, 217.
28. M. Dubey, V. K. Verma, K. Shanker, J. N. Sinha and K. P. Bhargava, *Die Pharmazie*, 1976, 34, 11; Vineet Malhotra, Seema Pathak, Rajendra Nath, Devashis Mukharjee and Kirpa Shanker, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2002, 41, 1310.
29. C. H. Collins, "Microbiological Methods", Butterworth, London, 1967, 364.
30. P. B. Godkar, "Text Book of Medical Laboratory Technology", Bhalavi Publication House, Mumbai, India, 1996, 326.
31. Robert Cruickshant, "A Practice of Medicinal Microbiology", Vol. II, p. 196.